

TRASH TALK: AWARENESS AND PRACTICES OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS ON SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN SAN MATEO, ISABELA

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the awareness and practices of solid waste management among Senior High School students in San Mateo, Isabela. It aims to determine whether the education provided in schools sufficiently equips students to manage solid waste effectively in their daily lives. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, targeting 146 students through a survey questionnaire. The results reveal that most respondents are highly aware of the importance of solid waste management, the 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle), and the adverse effects of improper waste disposal. Despite high awareness levels, the correlation between awareness and actual practices was found to be minimal to negligible. The study highlights partial compliance in recycling and proper waste disposal practices, indicating gaps in resources, facilities, and information dissemination. The findings underscore the need for enhanced education and community engagement to foster sustainable waste management habits among students. The study contributes to the understanding of solid waste management practices in the educational context, suggesting improvements for municipal SWM planning and implementation.

Keywords: *solid waste management, 3Rs, waste disposal*

INTRODUCTION

Solid waste management is collecting, transporting, or disposing of garbage materials. It pertains to the materials produced by human activities and the general method used to deal with the effects on the environment and health of human beings. In contrast, it promotes economic growth and raises the quality of life by minimizing or eliminating adverse effects on the environment and human beings (Paghasian, 2017). Due to population growth, improvements in the living standard, economic security, and industrialization, the Philippines' waste consumption grew gradually over the past year. The Philippines produces 0.40 kg of waste per individual. With this growth rate, waste production is projected to rise from 14.66 million tons in 2014 to 16.63 million tons in 2020, with Metro Manila being the primary source of that waste (Madrigal & Oracion, 2017).

In 2011, San Mateo Isabela received a national award for a zero waste management program. The municipality has Ordinance No. 2008-546, also known as the "Walang Plastikan Program," which bans the use of plastic bags and other non-biodegradable items in all local establishments, including the public market, as part of an effort to strengthen its zero-waste program. They encourage every citizen to bring their own "bayong," reusable plastic bag, or any bag to help lessen the problem. Waste management is required to diminish the growing crisis caused by solid waste, which damages society, endangers human life, and contaminates the environment. The Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000, also known as Republic Act No. 9003, which guarantees the proper segregation, collection, transport, and disposal of solid waste under the laws of conservation, public health, and other concerns, is one of the easiest things to lessen the impact of too much waste (Reyes & Madrigan, 2020). The repercussions of improper disposal could be dangerous. Therefore, there is a pressing need to educate young people about and raise awareness of environmental issues. Education enables people to become aware of the environment and the issues it raises. Students must be aware of environmental issues to efficiently fulfill their part in sustainable waste management (Fadhullah et al., 2022).

Understanding the concept of solid waste management will alter how people feel about rubbish. Waste should not be administered or addressed simply because it is waste. People grew up believing garbage is garbage; it should not be touched or approached. They once believed everyone's garbage should be in one container

(Bautista, 2019). Under Sections 55– 56 of RA 9003, known as the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act, the Philippine National Government is required to conduct extensive education and provide information about solid waste management (SWM) practices, as well as to deepen the ecological inclusion concerns in school curricula in collaboration with the Department of Education (DepEd) institutions, including colleges and universities and all levels. They promote environmental awareness and action among citizens by emphasizing waste management principles such as waste specificity, particularly resource conservation and recovery, segregation, reduction, reuse, recycling, reusing, and reducing (Lalamonan & Comighud, 2020).

Several studies have been conducted to determine whether the education and information received about solid waste management are practical and efficient. University students are knowledgeable about solid waste management. Although the students' awareness of proper waste management did not influence their disposal habits, it greatly impacted their practices, particularly regarding segregation, reduction, reuse, and recycling (Molina & Catan, 2021).

It is clear from this that the students at ISU-Cabagan Campus take substantial responsibility for reducing waste in their homes, using reliable yet affordable garbage cans, practicing waste recycling and selling the products, using waste recycling to improve the environment, composting biodegradable wastes, and regularly cleaning our surroundings to prevent disease. These signify that the pupils abide by solid waste management techniques and standards. However, it has been discovered that ISUC students are accountable for burning uncollected solid garbage in their residences (Peñaflor, 2020). Meanwhile, solid waste management studies in primary education are limited and have been given less attention. Hence, senior high school students of San Mateo were used in this investigation. The senior high school curriculum has recently been incorporated into fundamental education, which dates to R.A 9003.

Thus, this study investigated the awareness and practices of solid waste management among Senior High students at San Mateo, Isabela. Specifically, it aimed at determining whether the solid waste management practice taught in school is enough and applied in their daily lives. It examined whether their awareness and practices can prevent this environmental issue. Finally, this study aims to fill the various gaps in Solid Waste Management. Additionally, to develop an awareness and strategy and to strengthen waste education to change students' solid waste management habits and practices, it must consider the better understanding of the provision of RA 9003, known as Ecological Solid Waste Management.

METHODS

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to investigate the relationship between the awareness and practices of Senior High School students in San Mateo, Isabela, regarding solid waste management. This design explores the link between variables without suggesting causation, requiring data collection and analysis on at least two variables to identify any relationships.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents according to demographic details

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Female	84	58
Male	62	42
Age		
16 years old	30	21
17 years old	65	45
18 years old	35	24
19 years old	11	8
20 years old	4	3
Grade Level		
Grade 11	75	51
Grade 12	71	49
School		
SMVIHS	81	55
SMGCHS	65	45
No. of Household Members		
1-3 members	27	18
4-6 members	88	60

7-10 members	28	19
Others	3	2

The study targeted 146 Senior High School students from San Mateo Vocational Industrial High School and San Mateo General Comprehensive High School, selected through convenience sampling due to their availability during their immersion program. Table 1 shows that 58% of respondents are female, 45% are 17, 51% are in Grade 11, 55% attend SMVIHS, and 60% belong to households with 4-6 members.

Data was collected using a survey questionnaire adapted from Paghastian's (2017) study on solid waste management awareness and practices among college students. The questionnaire included demographic profile, awareness of solid waste management, and solid waste management practices.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the segregation area used by the respondents. As shown in the table, 79 percent of the respondents use their backyard as their segregation area; 25 or 17 percent use their front yard, while 5 or 3 percent use other areas for segregation. It suggests that most respondents use their backyard to segregate solid waste.

Table 2. Segregation Area Used by Respondents

Segregation Area	Frequency	Percentage
Front yard	25	17
Backyard	116	79
Others	5	3
Total	146	100%

Furthermore, the results imply that the respondents and their families observe waste segregation, given that designated areas are in their homes for such purposes. As Miguel (2022) indicated, the practice is highly promoted even at the barangay level since it is crucial in fostering proper waste management down to the grassroots level of the community.

Table 3. Garbage collection in Respondents' Residence

Garbage collection	Frequency	Percentage
Existent	39	27
Non-existent	107	73
Total	146	100%

The presence of garbage collection in the respondents' residences is shown in Table 3. Findings indicate that garbage collection services need to be more present in the residential area of 107 or 73 percent of the respondents. On the other hand, 39 or 27 percent of them reported an existent garbage collection mechanism in their place of residence. It shows that most of the respondents reside in locations where garbage is not collected in a standardized manner.

It was a problem highlighted in an article by Miguel (2022) for the DENR in which it was stated therein that although the enactment of RA 9003 or the Ecological Solid Waste Management has mandated LGUs to enforce solid waste management plans, the realization of said plans remains erratic as not all government units strictly enforce the law. This point is proven in the results indicated in Table 3, as more respondents stipulated that garbage collection is non-existent in their locality.

Respondents' Awareness of Solid Waste Management

Table 4 indicates the respondents' awareness regarding the importance of solid waste management. The data shows that the respondents are highly aware of the importance of solid waste management in terms of the reduction as the key to attaining a clean environment ($M=3.65$, $SD=0.57$). This means that students know that reducing waste can contribute to a clean environment. Followed by the Protection of public health ($M=3.54$) and the Protection of the public environment ($M=3.54$); the students are highly aware that the following can be achieved when they know how to put their waste in the right place, whereas the lowest-rated item was reproductive pests ($M=3.27$, $SD=0.59$); means that students are aware but their knowledge about this not enough. With this, a grand mean of 3.5 was computed, validating that the respondents demonstrate that they are highly aware of the importance of solid waste management.

Table 4. Respondents' Awareness of the Importance of Solid Waste Management

Indicator	M	SD	Description
1. Reduction of reproductive pest	3.27	0.59	Aware
2. Protection of public health	3.54	0.5	Highly aware
3. Protect public environment	3.55	0.5	Highly aware
4. Key to attaining a clean environment	3.65	0.57	Highly aware
Grand Mean	3.5	0.45	Highly aware

The said result is promising, considering that solid waste management remains one of the issues in the country, and the contribution of citizens towards the successful implementation of proper waste management starts with their awareness of the problems and issues related to it. As Jeremias and Fellizar (2020) stipulated in their study, solid waste management may be the responsibility of the municipal government. However, its effective and sustainable implementation can only be achieved through the participation and cooperation of the community members.

The table projects the respondents' awareness regarding the 3Rs of solid waste management. As shown in the table, the respondent is aware of the importance of recycling in Solid Waste Management (M=3.64, SD=0.56), interpreted as highly aware. It means that the student is willing to save and care for nature. Some of the recycling activities they do include decorating material using waste. It is followed by the importance of garbage reduction (M=3.62, SD=0.58), interpreted as highly aware, which means that the student is aware of the benefit that reducing waste can give. On the other hand, the least rated item is reusing (M=3.62, SD=0.05). Reusing is one of the ways we can reduce waste, and the students are aware of it but refuse to do it because it consumes their time.

Table 5. Respondents' Awareness of the 3Rs of Solid Waste Management

3 Rs	M	SD	Description
1. Reuse	3.62	0.5	Highly aware
2. Reduce	3.62	0.58	Highly aware
3. Recycle	3.64	0.56	Highly aware
Grand Mean	3.62	0.5	Highly aware

Generally, the students are highly aware of the awareness of 3rs, rated as 3.64, which makes them mindful and aware of protecting and preserving nature. Based on the study of Molina and Catan (2021), education and information dissemination are necessary to promote good solid waste management practices, especially among the younger generation. The fact that the respondents showed that they are often aware of the 3Rs bodes well for promoting solid waste management in the community.

Table 6 depicts the respondents' awareness regarding the benefits of recycling. As gleaned in the table, the respondents are aware of the benefits of recycling to the environment (M=3.6, SD=0.58). This means that the students know what our environment can gain from recycling, such as recycling paper and wood to save trees and forests, followed by the informal recyclers (M=3.25, SD=0.56). It means that the students know the benefits that informal recyclers receive by collecting solid waste. For example, they gain money from selling it. On the other hand, the least rated item was the municipality (M=3.34, SD=0.66), which means that the students see that their municipality has projects to reduce waste, such as making fences made of plastic bottles, etc., which makes their municipality environmentally friendly.

Table 6. Respondents' Awareness of the Benefits of Recycling

Benefits	M	SD	Description
1. Informal recycle	3.25	0.56	Aware
2. Municipality	3.34	0.66	Aware
3. Environment	3.6	0.58	Aware
Grand Mean	3.39	0.49	Aware

With a grand mean computed at 3.39, it is shown that the respondents are aware of the benefits of recycling to specific entities in the community. It concerns awareness is connected to practice, and the lack of recycling practices among locals is documented in the Philippines. In the study of Camarillo and Bellotindos (2021) alone, it was determined that there needs to be higher compliance in recycling, making waste management more challenging.

Table 7 above details the respondents' awareness of the information sources on solid waste management. Data shows that the respondents know that their school orientation (M=3.56, SD=0.54) and their parents (M=3.51, SD=0.61) can provide them with information about solid waste management. However, it was also determined that the respondents are aware that social media (M=3.27, SD=0.6), television (M=3.21, SD=0.66), research articles (M=3.16, SD=0.71), and peers/classmates (M=3.08, SD=0.66) can be sources of information for solid waste management.

Table 7. Respondents' Awareness of Information Sources for Solid Waste Management

Information	M	SD	Description
1. Parents	3.51	0.61	Highly Aware
2. School Orientation	3.56	0.54	Highly Aware
3. Peers or classmates	3.08	0.6	Aware
4. Television	3.21	0.6	Aware
5. Research Articles	3.16	0.71	Aware
6. Social Media	3.27	0.71	Aware
Grand Mean	3.3	0.42	Aware

As a grand mean of 3.3 was determined, it is signified that the respondents need to be made aware of other information sources for solid waste management. Similarly, information sources and dissemination were cited as needing more solid waste management implementation among barangays in the study by Camarillo and Bellotindos (2021).

Table 8 displays the respondents' awareness of the effects of improper waste disposal. Data analysis signifies that the respondents are highly aware of the adverse effects of human illness (M=3.55, SD=0.55) and severe threats to animals (M=3.51, SD=0.66). It means the students know the consequences of not putting their garbage in the right place for humans and animals. On the other hand, they are aware of improper waste disposal effects on the destruction of the environment (M=3.4, SD=0.83), clogging of canals (M=3.39, SD=0.72), and providing a breeding ground or shelter for pests (M=3.28, SD=0.73) which means that students have limited knowledge on what would be the outcome of throwing plastic in canals, etc. About the abovementioned findings, a grand mean of 3.43 was garnered, which signifies that the respondents need to be made aware of the effects of improper waste disposal.

As mentioned in previous discussions (Table 6), information dissemination needed to be improved; hence, the results cited in Table 9 are given. It validates the integral role of education and information dissemination in creating changes in the practices for proper waste management.

Table 8. Respondents' Awareness of the Effects of Improper Waste Disposal

Effect of Improper Waste Disposal	M	SD	Description
1. Human illness	3.55	0.55	Highly Aware
2. Serious threats to animals	3.51	0.66	Highly Aware
3. Destruction of the environment	3.4	0.83	Aware
4. Clogging of canals	3.39	0.72	Aware
5. Breeding or shelter of pests	3.28	0.73	Aware
Grand Mean	3.43	0.53	Aware

In Table 9, the respondents' awareness regarding the diseases resulting from improper waste disposal is indicated. Due to improper waste disposal, the respondents are highly aware of dengue ($M=3.59$, $SD=0.68$). This means that students know better that dengue disease is transmitted in an unsanitary environment. As for asthma ($M=3.41$, $SD=0.64$), malaria ($M=3.38$, $SD=0.71$), typhoid fever ($M=3.21$, $SD=0.71$), and congenital disability ($M=3.08$, $SD=0.74$), results suggest that the respondents are aware of these as consequences of improper waste disposal.

Table 9. Respondents' Awareness of Diseases Resulting from Improper Waste Disposal

Disease	M	SD	Description
1. Dengue	3.59	0.68	Highly Aware
2. Malaria	3.38	0.64	Aware
3. Typhoid fever	3.21	0.71	Aware
4. Birth defect	3.08	0.71	Aware
5. Asthma	3.41	0.74	Aware
Grand Mean	3.34	0.51	Aware

With a grand mean of 3.34, the respondents seldom know the diseases resulting from improper waste disposal. According to Molina and Catan (2021), developing public awareness of the adverse effects of improper waste disposal should be one of the primary focuses of information dissemination regarding solid waste management, as it will encourage people to participate in plans and programs. The senior high school curriculum currently includes lessons on these, but as the findings suggest, more emphasis must be placed on teaching these to students.

Table 10. Respondents' Awareness of Food Waste Use

Food Waste Use	M	SD	Descriptive
1. Fertilizer	3.53	0.66	Highly Aware
2. Food for animals (fish, etc.)	3.42	0.66	Aware
Grand Mean	3.47	0.57	Aware

The table above illustrates the respondents' awareness of the uses of food waste. The table shows that the respondents are aware that food waste can be used as fertilizer ($M=3.53$, $SD=0.66$). Also, the results show that the respondents know that food waste can be used for animal feed ($M=3.42$, $SD=0.66$). This means that the student knows alternative ways to deal with leftovers or spoiled food.

A grand mean of 3.47 was determined, suggesting that the respondents know the alternative uses of food waste. It is also reflected in the research conducted by Limon and Villarino (2020), which indicated that the lack of knowledge, facilities, and training contributed to the low participation of community members in reducing and recycling food waste. With this, the study suggested the collaboration of stakeholders in promoting practices for said issue.

Table 11. Respondents' Awareness of the Legal Bases Related to Solid Waste Management

Legal bases	M	SD	Descriptive
1. Presidential Decree No. 825 (Providing penalty for improper disposal of garbage and other forms of uncleanliness and for other purposes)	3.13	0.66	Aware
2. Presidential Decree No. 1586 (Establishing an environmental impact statement system, including other environmental management-related measures and for other purposes)	3.1	0.66	Aware
3. R.A No. 9003 (Ecological Solid Waste Management)	3.55	0.56	Aware

discussed in previous discussions in this study, information dissemination is vital to implementing waste management as it creates awareness and, ultimately, personal habit formation.

Respondents' Practices in Solid Waste Management

Table 14 shows the practices of the respondents in segregating waste. As gleaned from the figures, they often segregate biodegradable waste (M=4.41 SD=0.79), separate recyclable waste (M=4.38, SD=0.83), segregate recyclable items for collection and separate non-harmful wastes from toxic and hazardous wastes (M=4.26 SD=0.93).

Table 14. Respondents' Practices in Waste Segregation

Indicator	M	SD	Description
1. I segregate biodegradable (Paper, banana peels, cardboard, and vegetables) and non-biodegradable (plastic toys, glass, steel, rubber) waste at school.	4.41	0.79	Often
2. I separate recyclable waste (paper, cardboard, plastic bottles) from non-recyclable (food waste, leaves, twigs) waste at school.	4.38	0.83	Often
3. I separate non-harmful wastes from toxic and hazardous wastes such as pentel pens, laboratory chemicals, ink, cell batteries, and others.	4.26	0.93	Often
4. I mix all the garbage in one garbage container	3.32	1.49	Seldom
5. I segregate recyclable items for collection	3.81	1.19	Often
Grand Mean	4.03	0.62	Often

As for mixing all the garbage in one garbage container, results indicate that the respondents seldom practice this (M=3.32, Sd= 1.49). Further analysis revealed a grand mean of 4.03, suggesting that the respondents in school often observe waste segregation practices. Segregation has been promoted widely in Philippine schools by installing designated trash bins for different types of waste. It is a significant improvement as improper waste disposal in the country, which accumulates as litter in the environment, remains an issue in many municipalities and cities (Coracero et al., 2021).

Waste reduction practices observed by the respondents are summarized in Table 15. As shown in the table, the respondents Often engage in being cautious and responsible for every waste produced (M=4.29, SD=1.07), buying only what is needed so that extra food will not be thrown away (M=4.21, SD=1.1), bringing water in reusable water bottles than buying a single-use plastic bottle (M=4.06, SD=1.01); and borrowing, sharing, and renting things that are only occasionally needed (M=3.72, SD=1.03).

Table 15. Respondents' Practices in Waste Reduction

Indicator	M	SD	Description
1. I borrow, share, and/or rent things that are needed occasionally	3.72	1.07	Often
2. I buy only what I need so that I will not end up throwing away extra food	4.21	1.1	Often
3. I pack my lunch in a reusable lunch box so that I can't buy wrapped/packed food at school	4.21	1.01	Often
4. I bring water in reusable water bottles and then buy water in a single-use plastic bottle at the school.	4.06	1.03	Often
5. I am cautious and responsible for every waste I produce.	4.29	0.88	Often
Grand Mean	4.1	0.66	Often

Given these, a grand mean of 4.1 was obtained, signifying that the respondents often engage in waste reduction practices. It was also observed in the respondents of the study conducted by Aspiras et al. (2019), which mentioned that such practices contribute to the effectiveness of solid waste management in the community.

Table 16 presents the respondents' practices in reusing waste. It can be perceived in the table that the respondents often reuse washable food containers ($M=4.29$, $SD=0.94$), keep unfilled papers and use them as scratch ($M=4.14$, $SD=0.94$), reuse old materials rather than buy a new one ($M=4.12$, $SD=0.97$) and found that the respondents never reuse grocery bags ($M=1.49$, $SD=0.82$).

Table 16. Respondents' Practices in Reusing Waste

Indicator	M	SD	Description
1. I reuse my old materials rather than buying new ones.	4.12	1.02	Often
2. I kept those unfilled papers and used them as a scratch.	4.14	0.94	Often
3. I reuse grocery bags.	1.49	0.82	Never
4. I reuse washable food containers	4.29	0.97	Often
Grand Mean	3.51	0.55	Often

A grand mean of 3.51 was computed, denoting that the respondents Often reuse waste. In the study of Molina and Catan (2021), it was likewise indicated that students possessed enough knowledge regarding reusing waste, which was attributed to their school's initiatives. It provides an essential point for consideration in planning solid waste management activities as results indicate schools' vital role in promoting waste reuse among their stakeholders.

Table 17. Respondents' Practices in Recycling

Indicator	M	SD	Description
1. I convert or redesign waste materials into a new product.	3.88	1.02	Often
2. I make decors out of plastic wrappers and other colorful waste materials.	3.90	1.01	Seldom
3. I ignore the importance of recycling.	2.23	1.39	Rarely
4. I initiate generating income out of waste materials.	3.36	1.11	Seldom
Grand Mean	3.34	0.79	Seldom

In Table 17, the recycling practices of the respondents are presented. Data shows that the respondents Often convert or redesign waste materials into new products ($M=3.88$, $SD=1.02$). However, they Seldom make decorations out of plastic wrappers and other colorful waste materials ($M=3.36$, $SD=1.01$) and initiate income generation out of waste materials ($M=3.36$, $SD=0.94$). Results also indicated that they Rarely ignore the importance of recycling ($M=2.23$, $SD=1.11$). A grand mean of 3.34 was computed, implying that the respondents seldom practice recycling. Likewise, Aspiras et al. (2019) and Camarillo and Bellotindos (2021) also determined that recycling was seldom practiced in their respective studies. It denotes that more should be done to promote recycling among communities.

Table 18. Respondents' Practices in Proper Waste Disposal

Indicator	M	SD	Description
1. I throw and leave my garbage anywhere.	3.99	1.30	Often
2. I burn waste materials.	3.64	1.28	Often
3. I throw waste materials in common open dumps.	3.55	1.35	Often
4. I dispose of biodegradable waste in a compost pit.	3.35	1.35	Often
5. I dispose of hazardous/toxic/special wastes such as laboratory leftovers (chemicals) or electronic waste in any garbage container.	2.95	1.50	Seldom
Grand Mean	3.51	0.65	Seldom

The respondents' practices in proper waste disposal are summarized in the table above. As depicted, the respondents often throw and leave garbage anywhere ($M=3.99$, $SD= 1.30$), followed by them often burning waste materials ($M=3.64$, $SD= 1.28$). The respondents also often practiced throwing waste materials in common open dumps ($M=3.35$, $SD=1.35$) and disposed of their biodegradable waste in a compost pit ($M=3.35$, $SD=1.35$). The minor waste disposal practices that the respondents seldom dispose of are hazardous/toxic/special wastes such as laboratory leftovers (chemicals) or electronic waste in any garbage container. This means that the respondents know where to put their garbage correctly and what consequences their actions may bring to us and our environment.

Considering those above, a grand mean of 3.51 was attained, showing that the respondents often practice improper waste disposal. The results further signify that the respondents know that the abovementioned practices harm their environment, hence their avoidance of said activities. Regardless, the data still suggest a small extent of such practices, which calls for more reminders for them to stop engaging in such habits altogether.

Correlation among Variables

Data analysis shows that there is a positive correlation between the awareness of doing the 3Rs and the awareness of the benefits of recycling ($r=0.377$, $p<0.001$). Additionally, the awareness of different laws relevant to SWM shows a positive correlation with the awareness of the benefits of recycling ($r=0.388$, $p<0.001$). Moreover, the source of awareness on SWM is positively correlated with various awareness factors, including the benefits of recycling ($r=0.6$, $p<0.001$) and the effect of improper waste disposal ($r=0.504$, $p<0.001$). These correlations indicate that certain awareness factors are related and tend to coexist among respondents.

When examining the relationship between practices and awareness factors, it is found that waste reduction practices have a positive correlation with the awareness of the effect of improper waste disposal ($r=0.299$, $p<0.001$) and the uses of food waste ($r=0.338$, $p<0.001$). Similarly, waste reuse practices show a positive correlation with the uses of food waste ($r=0.299$, $p<0.001$) and programs, sanctions, funds, and policies related to SWM ($r=0.31$, $p<0.001$). These findings suggest that certain practices are associated with specific aspects of awareness in SWM.

The relationship between waste reuse practices and various aspects of SWM (solid waste management) is positive. There is an increase in the use of food waste and programs, sanctions, funds, and policies related to SWM when waste reuse is practiced. The awareness of the benefits of recycling and the different laws relevant to SWM also shows an increase, indicating a positive correlation between the two. It is further reinforced by the source of the awareness of SWM being positively correlated with the various awareness factors, such as the benefits of recycling and the effect of improper waste disposal on SWM practice.

With this correlation, it is evident that waste reuse practices are positively impacting SWM as there is an increase in awareness about the applicable laws and the benefits of recycling. It could lead to more people being mindful of their waste disposal and help contribute to sustainable waste management practices.

However, it is essential to note that not all practices exhibit significant correlations with awareness factors. For instance, waste recycling practices correlate weak or negligible with most awareness factors. Proper disposal practices also demonstrate weak or negligible correlations with awareness factors, except for a weak positive correlation with the awareness of prohibited activities ($r=0.158$, $p=0.057$). No matter how much students know about solid waste management, they still fail to practice proper disposal, reuse, and reduce waste. It could be due to a lack of convenience when following these fundamental practices or since they are not ingrained in the student's lifestyles. It may also be because the students are unaware of how much of an impact these practices could have or the long-term benefits of adhering to them.

Based on the provided correlations, awareness factors and practices in SWM are somewhat related. The positive correlations between certain practices and specific awareness factors support the notion that awareness can influence individuals' behaviors and practices in managing solid waste. However, the weak or negligible correlations observed in some cases indicate that other factors, such as socio-cultural influences and policy frameworks, may also play significant roles in shaping individuals' practices. Previous research indicates that awareness plays a crucial role in pro-environmental behaviors, such as practices in waste management (Schultz, 2002). This supports the hypothesis that awareness and solid waste management practices are closely interconnected.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis, the respondents demonstrated high awareness levels regarding the importance of solid waste management, including the 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle), benefits of recycling, information sources, effects of improper waste disposal, and the diseases that result from it. They were also aware of alternative uses of food waste, relevant laws, components of solid waste management, and prohibited activities related to waste management. However, there was partial compliance with recommended practices, particularly in recycling and proper waste disposal. This partial compliance is often due to a lack of resources, facilities, and information, which are critical areas for improvement in municipal SWM planning and implementation. Interestingly, the correlation between the respondents' awareness and their practices in solid waste management was minimal to negligible, suggesting that other factors might significantly impact both their awareness and practices. This aligns with findings from other studies, indicating that the relationship between awareness and practices can vary widely. Ultimately, while students across various strands have average knowledge of solid waste management, targeted education, and improved information dissemination could further enhance their habits and practices in this area.

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